

regenerated hills in the ratoon crop/total hills in the main crop) × 100] was evaluated 4 wk after main crop cutting.

Only 10 of 24 breeding lines showed regeneration. Ratooning ability varied from 59.4% to 94.9%, and ratoon growth duration from 49 to 61 d (see table). Thus, ratoon crop duration was 38-47% of that of the main crop. Ratoon height was slightly reduced but

ratoon grain yield did not significantly differ. RP1664-4461-693-1333 had the highest ratoon yield (1.7 t/ha), and IET7613 the lowest (0.8 t/ha) (see table). The reduction in ratoon grain yield was due primarily to smaller and fewer panicles.

The ratoon crop harvest — first week Oct — left ample time for the farmers to

plant another oilseed crop (rape or mustard), winter maize, or potato. But before adoption of rice ratooning in WS, the benefit-cost ratios of different cropping patterns — summer rice - ratoon rice - oilseed (or maize or potato) and summer rice - WS rice - oilseed (or potato or maize) — should be compared. □

Sequential tiller separation - a method for rapid rice seed multiplication

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To increase seed production of elite rice cultivars in a single season, we tried transplanting single tillers after repeatedly separating tillers. Five-day-old seedlings of 4 rice cultivars — PR103, PR106, PR109, and Basmati 370 — were transplanted 30 May 1986 at 40 seedlings each with 15- × 30-cm spacing. Each seedling developed 3-6 tillers within 18 d.

Effect of sequential tiller separation and transplanting on number of plants, yield, and seed multiplication ratio. Ludhiana, India, 1986 summer.

Split no.	Plants (no.)	Seed yield (kg/ha)	Seed multiplication ratio
<i>PR 103</i>			
0	10	1	200
1	40	5	781
2	116	10	1569
3	416	20	3302
<i>PR 106</i>			
0	10	1	250
1	52	6	1235
2	179	12	2598
3	659	42	9332
<i>PR 109</i>			
0	10	1	250
1	62	8	1468
2	225	20	3418
3	953	55	9705
<i>Basmati 370</i>			
0	10	1	125
1	38	5	481
2	97	9	931
3	390	19	1985

Thirty seedlings of each cultivar were uprooted and their tillers separated with a sharp razor (split 1). The separated tillers were retransplanted at 15- × 30-cm spacing in such a way that all tillers of every 10 uprooted seedlings formed one strip, for 3 strips/variety. The schematic propagation of PR109 is illustrated in the figure.

Ten days after the second transplanting, two strips of each variety were uprooted and the tillers separated (split 2). Those tillers were retransplanted 3 Jul. On 18 Jul, seedlings from one strip/cultivar were uprooted, tillers separated, and transplanted (split 3). Purple colored cultivar R575 was transplanted around all strips of all cultivars to control border effect.

The effect of sequential tiller splitting and transplanting on number of plants, seed yield, and seed multiplication ratio is given in the table. Maximum number of plants was from the original 10 seedlings of PR109, the minimum was with Basmati 370. Average increase in number of plants, irrespective of cultivar, was 62.

Seed yield did not increase in proportion to plant numbers. This may be due to reduced size and length of panicles, higher floret sterility, and reduced number of effective tillers. Increase in seed yield ranged from 16 times in Basmati 370 to 39 times in PR109, with an average of 27 times that of control.

Highest seed yield after the last split was 55 kg in PR109. Basmati 370 yielded 19 kg seed.

Sequential splitting and transplanting of rice tillers could help in rapid multiplication of elite and newly developed cytogenetic male sterile lines

for hybrid rice production. Small quantities of experimental hybrid rice seed also could be multiplied for testing across several locations in a single season. □

Schematic of single season vegetative propagation of rice cultivar PR109. Ludhiana, India, 1986 summer.